

Nitrogen trifluoride emissions in China from 2017 to 2021 derived from atmospheric observations

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Abstract

Rapid growth in the emissions of nitrogen trifluoride (NF₃), a potent greenhouse gas, poses a threat to the environment and climate system. This study estimated NF₃ emissions and their spatial distribution in China from 2017 to 2021 based on atmospheric observations from nine background stations in China, by employing a Lagrangian dispersion model-based Bayesian inversion technique. We found that NF₃ emissions in China increased from 0.95 (0.82–1.07) Gg yr⁻¹ in 2017 to 1.41 (1.28–1.55) Gg yr⁻¹ in 2021, representing a substantial growth of 48% over this period. The absolute increase in NF₃ emissions in China over 2017–2020, 0.65 (0.57–0.74) Gg yr⁻¹, is comparable to the increase in global emissions (0.63 (0.50–0.75) Gg yr⁻¹) over the same period. We identified substantial NF₃ emissions in the Pearl and Yangtze River Delta regions and Hubei Province, where well-established semiconductor industries could have contributed to NF₃ emissions. Moreover, large NF₃ emissions were identified in northern China, including Hebei, Henan, and Shandong Provinces. Increasing NF₃ emissions may delay China's progress toward achieving its carbon neutrality target by 2060 if control measures are not implemented.

42

43 **Keywords:** Nitrogen trifluoride, emissions, inverse modelling, fluorinated greenhouse gases

44

45 **Synopsis:** China's NF_3 emissions, derived from atmospheric observations and inverse

46 modelling, grew rapidly during 2017 to 2021.

47 Introduction

48 Nitrogen trifluoride (NF₃) is a potent greenhouse gas that is almost exclusively emitted from
49 anthropogenic sources^[1,2]. NF₃ is highly stable in the atmosphere, with a lifetime of 569 years^[3] and
50 a global warming potential on a 100-year scale of 17,700^[3,4]. Owing to its potential to impact the
51 global climate, NF₃ was added to the list of Annex A greenhouse gases through the Doha
52 Amendment to the Kyoto Protocol in December, 2012, and has subsequently been included in the
53 Paris Agreement.

54 NF₃ was first used in the 1960s as a fluorine supply for rocket fuel oxidizers and chemical
55 lasers^[5]. Since the late 1990s, NF₃ has been extensively employed as a fluoride cleaner in the
56 semiconductor industry and in the production of photovoltaic cells and flat panel displays
57 (FPDs)^[6,7]. NF₃ was chosen for the electronic industry because it was considered to be a more
58 promising and environmentally friendly gas than other conventional fluorine-containing gases (e.g.,
59 C₂F₆) owing to its higher etching efficiency and more stable and safe transport conditions^[8]. Thus,
60 NF₃ emissions increased along with growing demand for electronics between 1990 and 2015^[9,10],
61 and global NF₃ emissions increased from 2.0 ± 0.1 to 3.0 ± 0.1 Gg yr⁻¹ from 2016 to 2020^[4]. These
62 rising emissions have led to an acceleration in growth of global average NF₃ mole fractions, which
63 grew from 1.5 to 2.3 ppt between 2016 and 2020 and had an annual growth rate of 11.5% in 2020
64 relative to 2019^[4]. This rise in mole fraction has led to an increase in radiative forcing due to NF₃ of
65 nearly 60% from 2016 to 2020, reaching 0.48 mWm⁻² in 2020^[4].

66 China's semiconductor industry is growing rapidly, and its share of the global semiconductor
67 manufacturing capacity has quickly grown from 1% (1990–2000) to 15% (2010–2020)^[11]. China's
68 increase in semiconductor production is expected to account for 40% of the total increase in global
69 semiconductor production value over the next decade^[11]. The expanding semiconductor sector in
70 China is believed to be the source of the nation's rapid increase in NF₃ emissions in recent years.
71 Nevertheless, NF₃ emissions in China have not been well quantified^[12,13]. If emissions of NF₃ are
72 not constrained, it may exacerbate global warming.

73 The national inventory reports submitted by China to the United Nations Framework
74 Convention on Climate Change do not include NF₃^[14,15,16,17]. Three NF₃ emission estimates have
75 been compiled based on industry data in China (bottom-up inventories), including one by the
76 Emissions Database for Global Atmospheric Research (EDGAR)^[13], one by the U.S.
77 Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA)^[18], and the other by Guo et al.^[19]. However, the
78 magnitudes of emissions from China significantly differ between the three inventories, which is not
79 conducive to obtaining an accurate understanding of the current status of NF₃ emissions in China.
80 The reasons for the discrepancies might be the different inclusion of source sectors and different
81 application of activity data for electronic industry. Guo et al.^[19] covered more emission sectors than
82 EDGAR and US EPA, where NF₃ emissions from raw NF₃ production were not included. Although
83 top-down constraints from atmospheric observations can help to validate and improve the above
84 inventories, no time series of top-down emissions have been compiled using a network of
85 measurements made within China. Existing top-down estimates of NF₃ emission from China have
86 relied on atmospheric measurements made at locations outside of China^[1,12], and were not able to
87 quantify emissions from all regions within China.

88 In this study, we estimate yearly NF₃ emissions from the Chinese mainland (not including
89 emissions from Hong Kong, Macao, Taiwan and ocean regions) between 2017 and 2021, utilizing

90 data from nine Chinese sites and an inverse modelling approach. We examine the spatial
91 distribution of emissions, analyze connections between NF₃ emissions and the semiconductor and
92 FPD manufacturing industries, and estimate China's contribution to global NF₃ emissions.

93 **Materials and Methods**

94 **Sampling and analysis**

95 The measurement data were obtained from nine stations, denoted as Waliguan (WLG),
96 Shangdianzi (SDZ), Longfengshan (LFS), Lin'an (LAN), Shangri-La (XGL), Akedala (AKD),
97 Jinsha (JSA), Xinfeng (XFG), and Jiangjin (JGJ), operated by the China Meteorological
98 Administration (CMA). All stations are at least 10–20 km away from densely populated cities or
99 industrial zones, and sample inlets are mounted at the tops of sampling towers (80 m for WLG, SDZ,
100 and LFS; 50 m for LAN, XGL, AKD, JSA, and XFG; and 10 m for JGJ) to avoid local
101 contamination and ensure regional representativeness. Measurements at these sites are sensitive to
102 surface emissions over most industrial regions of China (See Figure S1). More site information can
103 be found in Table S1 and previous studies^[20,21,22].

104 The sampling and analysis process has been described before^[21] and is briefly summarized
105 here. Weekly samples were collected at AKD, LFS, JSA, SDZ, WLG, XFG, and XGL, and daily
106 samples were collected at JGJ. At LAN, weekly samples were collected before December 2018 and
107 daily after this date. Ambient air samples were collected in a 3 L stainless steel tank (X23-2N,
108 LabCommerce, Inc., San Jose, CA, USA) through a 10 mm OD sampling tube (Synflex-1300, Eaton
109 Corp., Cleveland, OH, USA). From the top of the sampling tower, the air sample passed through a
110 membrane pump (KNF-86, KNF Neuberger GmbH, Freiburg, Germany) and was then sent to the
111 CMA laboratory in Beijing for analysis. At SDZ, in addition to the abovementioned weekly flask
112 sampling, the mixing ratio of NF₃ was measured every 2 h in situ from 2017 to 2021. All flask
113 samples and in situ samples were analyzed using a Medusa gas chromatography/mass spectrometry
114 (GC/MS) system^[6], with an automated custom-built GC system coupled with MS detection (Agilent
115 6890/5975B, Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA)^[6,23]. The measurement precision of NF₃
116 was estimated to be 3.5% for flask samples and 2% for in situ measurement. The atmospheric
117 observations used to derive the emissions are shown in Figure S2.

118

119 **Regional transport model and sensitivity**

120 To estimate NF₃ emissions in China, a top-down approach based on atmospheric observations
121 and inverse modelling was used. This inversion approach and its application to other compounds in
122 the CMA dataset has been detailed in previous studies^[24,25]. The inversion framework can be
123 expressed by equation (1):

124

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{e}$$

125

126 where \mathbf{y} consists of the measured mole fractions from all sites; \mathbf{H} is the sensitivities of the
127 measurements to surface emissions, as well as the sensitivities of the measurements to the domain
128 boundary conditions; \mathbf{x} is the targeted parameter that we want to solve, which contains surface
emissions and boundary conditions; \mathbf{e} represents the model-measurement error.

129 The inversion was solved annually. For the measurements (y in equation (1)), we incorporated
130 all the measurements for each year from the nine sites into one matrix for the inversion, where the in
131 situ measurement at SDZ which were averaged every 24 hour to reduce the auto-correlated errors.
132 Although the measurement periods/frequencies of these sites are different, their sensitivities to
133 emissions have not shown significant interannual variations (see Figure S1). We used the
134 Numerical Atmospheric Dispersion Modelling Environment (NAME) developed by the UK Met
135 Office^[26,27] to quantify the relationship between emission sources and atmospheric measurements
136 (i.e., sensitivities \mathbf{H} in equation (1)). The NAME model was run backward for 30 days, driven by the
137 global-scale meteorological data output from the UK Met Office Unified Model (UM)^[28]. The
138 computational domain spanned from 5°S to 74°N and from 55°E to 192°E, encompassing a
139 sufficient range to cover the transport of air particles over the concerned region. The spatial
140 resolution of the grids in the domain was 0.234° in latitude and 0.352° in longitude. Particles were
141 released at a rate of 20,000 particles/h from each sampling time, within a vertical range of ± 10 m
142 from the sampling location. During transport within the computational domain, particles 0–40 m
143 above the ground were regarded as interacting with surface emissions, and their residence times
144 were integrated to calculate the sensitivity of each measurement to surface emissions within the
145 computational domain. The locations where particles passed the boundaries of the computational
146 domain were also recorded to calculate the sensitivity of each measurement to the boundary
147 conditions (background values) (included in \mathbf{H} in equation (1)). NF_3 was considered to be inert
148 during transport due to its long atmospheric lifetime of 569 years.

149

150 **Inversion algorithm and a priori information**

151 A hierarchical Bayesian inference approach^[29,30] was employed to estimate NF_3 emissions in
152 China, which utilized a priori information to constrain posterior emissions.

153 The a priori magnitude of NF_3 emissions in China used in the inversion was assumed to be 1
154 Gg yr^{-1} and to remain constant throughout the entire period, which was similar to the reported
155 magnitude of NF_3 emissions in China in previous studies^[1,19]. The spatial allocation of total
156 emissions was determined using the Defense Meteorological Satellite Program-Operational
157 Linescan System (DMSP-OLS) nighttime lights dataset obtained from the National Oceanic and
158 Atmospheric Administration (NOAA)-National Geophysical Data Center website
159 (https://ngdc.noaa.gov/eog/data/web_data/v4composites/). The nighttime lights density data
160 represent the artificial illumination visible from space in the dark, which provides an indicator of
161 potential emissions associated with densely populated areas and industrial parks.

162 NF_3 emissions were estimated in the inversion by scaling the a priori emissions in each of 150
163 basis functions, which were determined by applying a quadtree algorithm^[31] to the a priori
164 contribution from each grid to measurements. The prior probability for scaling factors in each basis
165 function was assumed to follow a log-normal distribution with shape parameters $\mu = 0.2$ and
166 $\sigma = 0.8$. This distribution effectively constrained the scaling within a realistic range (within one
167 order of magnitude) while ensuring positive values.

168 The a priori boundary conditions (background values) were calculated using NAME
169 sensitivities to the four horizontal domain boundaries, as described in the above section, and the
170 monthly background mole fractions obtained from a global 12-box model^[32,33]. The scaling factors
171 for the boundary conditions followed a log-normal distribution with shape parameters $\mu = 1$ and
172 $\sigma = 1$. The model-measurement uncertainties (e in equation (1)) were also solved in the

173 inversion, with the model uncertainty following a uniform distribution between 0 and 30 ppt, and
174 the measurement uncertainties fixed in the inversion at a value estimated from instrumental
175 precisions.

176 In order to solve the Bayesian inversion, we utilized the Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC)
177 technique. Following a preliminary tuning period of 1.25×10^5 iterations, a total number of $2.5 \times$
178 10^5 iterations for MCMC sampling was established. To prevent potential biases in the initial phase
179 of the Markov chain, the first 5×10^4 samples from the chain were excluded. NF_3 emissions and
180 their associated uncertainties are presented as the mean value and corresponding 68% uncertainty
181 interval (16%–84%, denoting 1 standard deviation for Gaussian uncertainties) derived from the
182 Markov chain.

183

184 Results and Discussion

185 NF_3 emissions in China

186 Our study revealed an increase of 0.47 (0.28 – 0.65) Gg yr^{-1} in NF_3 emissions in China from
187 2017 to 2021 (Figure 1). NF_3 emissions increased from 0.95 (0.82 – 1.07) Gg yr^{-1} in 2017 to 1.41
188 (1.28 – 1.55) Gg yr^{-1} in 2021, representing an overall growth of 48%. Note that there is a slight drop
189 in NF_3 emission in 2021. We are unable to explicitly explain the reason for the drop, which could
190 also be an artefact of the model-measurement uncertainties and need to be further inspected in the
191 future.

192

193 **Figure 1.** Comparison of NF_3 emissions in China derived in this study with those of other studies^[12,13, 18, 19], EDGAR
194 v7.0^[13] and the United States Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA)^[18] inventories reported nearly negligible
195 NF_3 emissions from the electronics industry in China. A bottom–up analysis for 2010–2019 (blue line) conducted by
196 Guo et al.^[19] considered NF_3 emissions from the semiconductor, FPD, and photovoltaics manufacturing industries.
197 Arnold et al.^[12] only reported top-down 2014 and 2015 NF_3 emissions.

198

199 Large differences were observed among the three bottom-up inventory-based studies, Guo et
200 al.^[19], EDGAR v7.0^[13], and the US EPA inventory^[18]. For example, Guo et al.^[19] reported 1.69 Gg
201 yr⁻¹ for China's NF₃ emissions in 2019, which was 40 times higher than those reported by EDGAR
202 v7.0^[13], and 6 times higher than those of US EPA^[18]. The lower estimated NF₃ emissions in the US
203 EPA^[18] and EDGAR^[13] inventories could be due to incomplete accounting for some source sectors,
204 inaccuracies in activity data, and underestimation of emission factors. Top-down estimates of NF₃
205 emissions based on atmospheric measurements can be beneficial for quality assurance of national
206 inventories, as recommended by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change guidelines^[40]. Our
207 top-down emission estimates aligned well with the bottom-up estimates by Guo et al.^[19] between
208 2017 and 2019, although our values were slightly lower (about 4%–14% lower) than their reported
209 best estimates. Notably, the results in our study and Guo et al.'s emission estimates both
210 demonstrated a rapid increase in China's NF₃ emissions between 2017 and 2019. However, there
211 were few previous results before 2017 available for comparison, making validation of the emissions
212 increase since these early years difficult. A previous study by Arnold et al.^[12] estimated China's NF₃
213 emissions for 2014 and 2015 through inverse modelling. The uncertainty in their results was very
214 large, and their emissions were over a period that does not overlap with the study, which makes it
215 difficult to draw comparisons between their estimates and those presented in this work.

216 **Spatial distribution of NF₃ emissions**

217 According to the spatial distribution of NF₃ emissions in China derived from atmospheric
218 measurements (see Figures 2, S3 and S4), areas of high emission were identified in northern China
219 at the junction of southern Hebei Province, southern Henan Province, and western Shandong
220 Province, as well as in the Yangtze River Delta region and the Pearl River Delta regions (The
221 locations of six provinces in China are shown in Figure S5). The Yangtze River Delta and the Pearl
222 River Delta regions are characterized by high population densities, high economic development,
223 and intensive semiconductor manufacturing. These factors likely explain why these two regions
224 contributed substantially to the national emissions increase in between 2017 and 2021 (Figure 2c).
225 The electronics industry mainly includes the production of mobile telecommunication handsets,
226 microcomputer equipment, Integrated circuits and color television sets. Their annual production
227 data during the study period by province are provided by China industry statistical yearbook^[34-38]
228 and summarized in Table S2 to S5, respectively. High NF₃ emissions in the Yangtze River Delta
229 were mainly concentrated in Jiangsu Province, which could be attributed to Jiangsu Province's
230 developed integrated circuit (IC) and FPD manufacturing industries^[34-38]. NF₃ emissions in Jiangsu
231 Province increased over the study period by 0.016 (0–0.076) Gg yr⁻¹, an increase of 16%. The NF₃
232 emissions in the Pearl River Delta were similar to that in the Yangtze River Delta, with the main
233 mature semiconductor industry concentrated in Guangdong Province^[34-38]. NF₃ emissions in
234 Guangdong province increased from 0.063 (0.021–0.11) Gg yr⁻¹ in 2017 to 0.092 (0.035–0.15) Gg
235 yr⁻¹ in 2021, a growth rate of 46%. Note that the increasing trend is not significantly different
236 ($p > 0.05$) from zero due to large uncertainties of the emission estimates on provincial level. A dense
237 observation network in the key source regions will help reduce the uncertainties in the derived
238 emissions and help quantify the changing rate. High NF₃ emissions were also commonly identified
239 throughout 2017–2021 in the southern part of Hebei Province, southern Henan Province, and
240 western Shandong Province in northern China. The NF₃ emissions in these three provinces
241 increased by 0.29 (0.22–0.37) Gg yr⁻¹ from 2017 to 2021, an increase that accounts for about nearly

242 62% of the increase in national emissions. However, local production of ICs and FPDs in this region
 243 was low, and are therefore not likely the source of the high level of NF_3 emissions^[34-38], and
 244 suggests that highly emissive factories or other sources of NF_3 emissions may have been present in
 245 the area. In addition to the three areas of high emission mentioned above, Hubei Province, located in
 246 the central region of China, also exhibited high NF_3 emissions, which may have been related to
 247 rapid development of the semiconductor industry in that province^[34-38] and the Hubei provincial
 248 government's strong support for the semiconductor/FPD industry^[39]. NF_3 emissions in Hubei
 249 Province increased from 0.023 (0.0010–0.039) Gg yr^{-1} in 2017 to 0.10 (0.05–0.16) Gg yr^{-1} in 2021,
 250 an increase of 0.08 (0.025–0.13) Gg yr^{-1} .

251
 252 **Figure 2.** Spatial distribution of NF_3 emissions in China. a. Average NF_3 emissions in 2017–2018. b. Average NF_3
 253 emissions in 2019–2021. c. Difference between a and b. Black circles represent active measurement sites during the
 254 time period, while gray inverted triangles represent known semiconductor factories in China
 255 (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_semiconduct%20or_fabrication_plants, last access: 7 December 2023).

256 Contribution of China's NF₃ emissions to global emissions

257 Figure 3 compares China's NF₃ emissions with global total emissions^[4]. China's share of
258 global emissions increased from 41% in 2017 to a peak contribution of 54% in 2020.

259 Between 2017 and 2020, China's NF₃ emissions increased by 0.65 (0.57–0.74) Gg yr⁻¹, which
260 was comparable to the independently estimated global emission growth of 0.63 (0.50–0.75) Gg yr⁻¹
261 over the same period. This suggests that the increase in China's NF₃ emissions explained all of the
262 growth in global emissions over 2017 to 2020.

263

264 **Figure 3.** Global NF₃ emissions (black line and grey shading, representing 1-sigma uncertainties), emissions from
265 China (red line, star-shaped markers and red shading), and China's percentage contribution to global NF₃ emissions
266 during 2017–2021 (purple dashed line and squares, right axis). Global NF₃ emissions were obtained from Laube and
267 Tegtmeier, (2022) ^[4].

268

269 We deem it most likely that rise in global NF₃ emissions is due to the rapid growth of the
270 global semiconductor industry^[11]. However NF₃ emissions slightly decreased in 2021, which is not
271 consistent with the continuously increasing trend of Chinese production of semiconductor
272 industry^[34-38]. We are unable to explain the decrease in emissions in China in 2021, which could
273 be genuine or an artifact due to model-measurement errors. As of 2021, NF₃ emissions in China are
274 equivalent to approximately 25 million tonnes of CO₂-equivalent emissions (calculated using the
275 100-year GWP^[4]), highlighting a large impact from China's NF₃ emissions on global climate. With
276 rising demand for NF₃ in the semiconductor industry in the coming years, control measures could
277 help to mitigate NF₃'s impact on climate, thus contributing to China's ambition to mitigate global
278 warming as outlined in its carbon neutrality target by 2060.

279

280 **Data Availability**

281 NF_3 measurement data from the Chinese network are provided in the Supporting
282 Information, Data file 1. Use of China's measurement data in publications, reports, or presentations
283 requires potential users to first contact Bo Yao (yaobo@fudan.edu.cn) to discuss their interests.

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